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Net Income Inequality in the Italian Regions between 2004-2020

It grew on average by 4.83%

Istat calculates the value of net income inequality. The value is the ratio between the total equivalent income received by the 20% of the population with the highest income and that received by the 20% of the population with the lowest income. The data refers to the period 2004-2020 for the 20 Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of net income inequality in 2020. Campania is in first place by value of net income inequality in 2020 with a value of 7.5 units, followed by Sicily with an amount of 7.2 and Calabria with an amount equal to 6.4 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont and Tuscany with an amount of 4.7 units and Veneto with a value of 4.5 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of 4.1 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 4.00 units and Marche with a value of 3.7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in net income inequality between 2004 and 2020. Campania is in first place by value of the percentage change in net income inequality between 2004 and 2020 with an amount equal to 20.97% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.2 units up to a value of 7.5 units. Puglia follows with a change in net income inequality equal to an amount of +17.65% corresponding to a change from an amount of 5.1 units up to a value of 6.00 units. Below is Tuscany with a variation equal to an amount of 17.50% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.00 units up to a value of 4.7 units. In the middle of the table are Sicily with a value equal to 4.35% and a variation from an amount of 6.9 units up to a value of 7.2 units, followed by Lombardy with a variation equal to an amount of 4, 08% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.9 units up to a value of 5.1 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 2.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.1 units up to a value of 4.2 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -4.65%, followed by Marche with a value of -9.76% and Basilicata with an amount of -12.24%. On average, the value of net income inequality grew between 2004 and 2021 from an amount of 4.87 units to a value of 5.1 units or equal to a growth of 4.83%.

Net income inequality in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2020. The value of net income inequality grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2020. Specifically, it increased in the North with a value of 4.26%, in the North West for a value of 6.12%, in the North-East with a value of 2.27%, in Central Italy and Southern Italy with a value of 8.33%, in the South for a amount of 12.28% and in the Islands for 6.06%. The data therefore suggests a worsening of the conditions of material equality in the Italian macro-regions. However, we can see that inequality in the southern regions tends to be higher than inequality in the northern regions. And probably, beyond a certain point, inequality becomes a limit to economic growth and social development. The southern regions are therefore affected not only by a lower per capita income than that of the northern regions. The southern regions are also characterized by a process of centralization of incomes so that in Southern

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Italy the richest 20% have 6.4 times the income of the poorest 20% while the same ratio for the North is equal to 4.9.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Marche, Trentino Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Abruzzo, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Liguria, Basilicata, Puglia, Molise, Sardinia
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Lazio.

From the point of view of clustering we can note the following ordering: $C2 > C1$. It follows that the level of inequality in 3 southern regions and Lazio tends to be significantly higher than the level of inequality in the centre-north. That is, regions that tend to have medium-low incomes also have high levels of inequality. Inequality in these cases could be considered as a contributing cause of low per capita profitability. In fact, it is very likely that there is a level of inequality beyond which the economy stops functioning. In fact, the regions that have higher levels of per capita income are also the regions that have lower inequality. That is, it is very likely that the path to access economic growth passes through economic policies aimed at reducing economic inequalities.

Conclusions. In summary, we can see how inequality has grown in the Italian regions in the period considered, i.e. between 2004 and 2020. In particular, inequality is present in the southern regions or in the areas of Italy with the lowest per capita income. The regions of Northern Italy are characterized by levels of net income inequality that are much lower than those of the Southern regions. It is therefore very likely that the elimination of the gap between Northern and Southern Italy will involve a reduction in income inequalities. However, since the top 20% of the southern regions is made up of both the public and private ruling class, it is very unlikely that this ruling group will decide to reduce its economic prospects for the benefit of the population. There is therefore a problem of the quality of the southern ruling classes, which appear to be truly inferior, compared to the northern ruling classes. And indeed we could use the differential in income inequality between northern and southern regions as a yardstick to evaluate the redistributive efficiency of the southern ruling class. A value that would certainly be negative for Southern Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

